

Note on an incorrectly recorded provider of source materials in a Transgas publication

In the publication *Transgas: Areál řídicího ústředny Tranzitního plynovodu a budova FMPE v Praze* (in English language *Transgas; The area of the control center of the Transit gas pipeline and the FMPE building in Prague*) published by the National Heritage Institute in 2019 (ISBN 978-80-7480-138-9),¹ the name of Mr. Jan Lochman is incorrectly spelled. Therefore, the correct name should be *Jan Lochman*, not *Jan Lochmann*. This information is confirmed in its apology by the editors of the publication, published online on the National Heritage Institute e-shop.²

Mr. Lochman used his own finances to acquire three period volumes from 1966³ containing photographs and drawings of the designs for the headquarters of the *Plynárenské podniky* (Gas Companies enterprise), which emerged from an architectural competition. The third-prize winners, Ivo Loos and Jindřich Malátek, were then invited to join Jiří Eisenreich's team, where a new design for the complex, later known as Transgas, was developed.⁴ Mr. Lochman provided these materials to the authors of the chapter, *Soutěž na Ústřední plynárenský dispečing v Praze* (Competition for the Central gas dispatching office in Prague), free of charge. They drew from these materials and used reproductions. Of the 22 image reproductions of this 16-page chapter, 18 images are used by the chapter authors from Mr. Lochman's materials.

Mr. Lochman's name is mentioned in the text, footnotes, reproduction captions, and in the name list, but unfortunately incorrectly with two n's. This entry serves as a public clarification.

1 Naďa Goryczková, ed., *Transgas: Areál řídicího ústředny Tranzitního plynovodu a budova FMPE v Praze*, 1st ed. (Národní památkový ústav, 2019). (in Czech)

2 "Transgas. Areál řídicího ústředny Tranzitního plynovodu a budova FMPE v Praze. Historie | architektura | urbanismus," Národní památkový ústav, n.d., <https://web.archive.org/web/20250421214203/https://npu.cz/cs/e-shop/61189-transgas-areal-ridici-ustredny-tranzitniho-plynovodu-a-budova-fmpe-v-praze-historie-architektura-urbanismus>. (in Czech)

3 These are Czech publications *Architektonická soutěž na ideový návrh budovy ÚPD v Praze: Oceněné návrhy; Užší architektonická soutěž na budovy ÚPD v Praze*; and *Výhodnocené návrhy v prvním kole soutěže na ideový návrh budovy ÚPD v Praze*.

4 Lukáš Beran, "TRANSYGAS: Budovy Ústředního dispečinku tranzitního plynovodu, Federálního ministerstva paliv a energetiky a Světové odborové federace," *Archiweb*, n.d., accessed February 1, 2026, <https://www.archiweb.cz/b/transgas-budovy-ustredniho-dispecinku-tranzitniho-plynovodu-federalniho-ministerstva-paliv-a-energetiky-a-svetove-odborove-federace>. (in Czech)